

Horizon 2020

Research and Innovation Framework Program

CHESSETUP

Deliverable 3.3. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION REPORT

Deliverable Type: Public
Date: 24/07/2018
Distribution: WP3
Editors: Lavola
Contributors:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 680556.

List of authors

Partner	Authors
Lavola	Eloi Montcada
	Esteve Maneja
	Cristina Bayés
	Mar Miralles

Document history

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
16/12/2016	1	Lavola		Draft
21/12/2016	2	Lavola		Final version
24/07/2018	3	Lavola		Reviewed version

Table of Contents

System configuration report	2
1. Introduction	2
2. Reference case configuration.....	3
2.1. Solar radiation to direct use tank (buffer tank)	9
2.2. Solar radiation to seasonal energy storage tank (STES).....	10
2.3. Seasonal storage energy tank to direct use tank.....	10
2.4. Boiler as a backup	13
3. System configuration analysis	13
3.1. Modes of operation.....	14
3.2. Collector's slope.....	20
3.3. Minimum collector's surface to maximize the heat capacity of the seasonal tank	21
3.4. Storage and buffer tank's thermal losses	25
3.5. Direct use tank size (buffer tank)	26
3.6. De/Centralized configuration.....	27
3.7. Climate conditions	29
4. System configuration conclusions	31
4.1. Modes of operation.....	32
4.2. Collectors' slope.....	33
4.3. Collectors' surface.....	34
4.4. Thermal losses	34
4.5. Direct use tank.....	35
4.6. De/centralized system	35
4.7. Climate conditions	35
5. Annex 1: Trnsys simulation graphs results	36
6. Annex 2: Trnsys types	44

System configuration report

1. Introduction

The objective of CHESS SETUP (Combined HEat SyStem by using Solar Energy and heat pUmPs) project is to design, implement and promote a reliable, efficient and profitable system able to supply heating and hot water in buildings.

CHESS SETUP system is composed by several components such as solar panels, long term heat storage, heat pumps and other elements, which should be related in size and proportionally customized when configuring an optimal solution for a particular implementation of the system.

This document aims to be a report comparing technical and economical details for the different parts of a reference case system configuration under particular cases.

There are some key issues regarding the configuration of the system which can affect notably its energy performance, investment costs and comfort for the building users. In order to determinate the optimal solution in these terms, and beyond the preliminary system sizing tested in the deliverables D3.1. and D3.2, one reference case of the system configuration has been simulated using the Trnsys simulation software¹.

Once decided the main characteristics of the system components and modelled the reference case configuration using the Trnsys simulation software, some parameters of these components have been analyzed in order to determinate the optimal solution for this reference case. Different climate conditions have been also considered in the analysis.

The simulations carried out using this simulation software have the purpose of analysing the performance of the different components inside a complex system that operate under imposed conditions. The modification of this conditions as well as the characteristics of the components used, have a huge impact on the global performance of the system, so each change or adjustment of the configuration should be carefully considered.

The optimal configuration will be used for having a more precise sizing in the pilot experiences.

¹ Simulation studio. Version 5.4.0.0. Trnsys Version: 17.02.0005.

2. Reference case configuration

The reference case configuration considered for the simulation purpose of this report consists of the following elements:

- Solar thermal collectors (STC) that can be used to heat a direct use tank (buffer tank) or to heat a seasonal thermal energy storage (STES) tank, depending on the solar radiation and the heating and domestic hot water demand.
- A high efficiency heat pump which is used to increase the temperature of the water of the seasonal tank to provide hot water to the buffer tank, if there's no solar energy available or if it is not enough energy stored to cover the demand. The Heat Pump characteristics have been retrieved from the results of the deliverable D3.4.
- A natural gas boiler that operates ultimately and after the buffer tank when it has not been possible to reach the temperature required to satisfy the heating and domestic hot water demand with the solar energy or the energy stored.

Figure 1: Reference case configuration

Table 1: Basic characteristics of the reference case configuration

Elements and data	Basic characteristics of the reference case configuration
Location	North-East of Spain (latitude 40°) Average annual temperature: 12.5°C Total annual irradiation on horizontal: 1.693 kWh/m ² Operation hours/year: 8.760 hr Peak load: 173,2 kW
Total demand	Heat and hot water demand: 263.655,9 kW/year (100 family units)
Solar Thermal Collector (STC)	Collectors surface: 200m ² Orientation: south Slope: 40°
Heat transfer fluid (solar collectors)	Water
Heat Exchanger	Plate heat exchanger Performance: 100%
Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage Tank (STES)	Volume = 3 x Collectors surface = 600m ³ Cylindrical shape
Heat Pump	Thermal capacity: 905.750 kJ/hr Power capacity: 270.857 kJ/hr Coefficient of performance (COP): 3 (annual average value) Water flow: 4.8l/s (evaporator) and 8.3l/s (condenser)
Direct Use Tank (Buffer tank)	Volume: 0.05 x Volume Storage tank = 30 m ³ Cylindrical shape
Boiler	Maximum heating rate: 400.000 kJ/hr

The reference case configuration modelled in the Trnsys simulation includes the following types and base information. For more details see Annex 2: Trnsys types on this report.

Table 2: Basic characteristics of the Trnsys types used in the simulation

Elements and data	Basic characteristics of the Trnsys types used in the simulation
Location	<p>For the reference case the weather file used was the annual data collected in the weather station in Gurb (Latitude: 41.95, Longitude: 2.2167) by the public weather agency in Catalonia. (Meteocat²). The type used was:</p> <p>Solar Radiation Processor: Total Horizontal, Temperature and Relative Humidity Known. Type 16c. See Table 4.</p> <p>For the other locations the type used was:</p> <p>Weather Data Processor; Combines data reading, radiation processing and sky temperature calculations. Type 15-6. See Table 5.</p>
Total demand	<p>Demand file per hour from a reference case of 100 family units. See Graph 22.</p> <p>Data Reader For Generic Data Files. Type 93. See Table 6.</p>
Solar Thermal Collector (STC)	<p>Glazed Flat Plate Collectors. Quadratic Efficiency Approach. Type 539. See Table 7.</p>
Heat Exchanger	<p>Heat Exchanger with User-Provided Effectiveness. Type 91b. See Table 8.</p>
Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage Tank (STES)	<p>Storage Tank; Fixed Inlets, Uniform Losses. Type 4a. See Table 9.</p>
Heat Pump	<p><i>Water-to-Water Heat Pump - Normalized Data File Approach. Type 927. See</i></p>

² The Meteorological Service of Catalonia (SMC, Servei Meteorològic de Catalunya in Catalan, also known as Meteocat) is a public company ascribed to the Department of Territory and Sustainability of the Government of Catalonia (Spain). It is the organisation responsible for the observation system and meteorological forecast in Catalonia. It is an associate member of the European Meteorological Society (EMS).

Elements and data	Basic characteristics of the Trnsys types used in the simulation
	Table 10.
Direct Use Tank (Buffer tank)	<i>Storage Tank; Fixed Inlets, Uniform Losses. Type 4a. See Table 11.</i>
Boiler	Auxiliary heater. Type 6. See Table 12.

Figure 2: Trnsys scheme

The reference case configuration modelled in the Trnsys simulation software operates in the different ways explained below depending on the solar radiation availability and the heating and hot water demand:

- Solar radiation to direct use tank (buffer tank)
- Solar radiation to seasonal energy storage tank (STES)
- Seasonal storage energy tank to direct use tank
- Boiler as a backup

2.1. Solar radiation to direct use tank (buffer tank)

The main objective of this operation mode is to take full advantage of the solar radiation to heat directly the buffer tank, when it is possible.

If there is heat demand and sufficient solar radiation, the solar collectors can directly supply the energy needed using the bypass circuit. If the difference between the temperature that comes out of the solar collectors and the temperature in the cold side of the direct use tank is equal or higher than 5°C, WP₅ and WP₁ turn ON and the system works to heat the direct use tank through the heat exchanger, as a bypass of the seasonal storage tank. When the temperatures difference is lower than 1°C, WP₅ and WP₁ stop. Both water pumps also turns OFF when the water that comes out of the direct use tank reaches 70°C because it is hot enough to ensure the heating and hot water demand.

Figure 3: Solar radiation to direct use tank (Bypass circuit)

This bypass circuit has priority over all the other modes of operation so the solar energy can be harnessed to the maximum.

2.2. Solar radiation to seasonal energy storage tank (STES)

During periods of low demand and high solar radiation, the energy production does not fit the energy demand. Then, the system can accumulate thermal energy for later utilization through the thermal energy storage tank.

When there is no heat demand but enough solar radiation, the solar collectors can charge the seasonal energy storage tank, heating the water which is inside. This charging circuit operates turning ON WP2 and WP1 when the difference between the temperature that comes out of the solar collectors and the temperature in the cold side of the storage tank is higher than 12°C, but only if WP5 is OFF (so the bypass circuit is not working). When the temperatures difference is lower than 4°C, WP2 turns OFF in order to not cool down the water stored in the tank. If the water in the hot side of the storage tank reaches 90°C, WP2 turns OFF so the charging mode stops.

Figure 4: Solar radiation to STES tank (Charging circuit)

2.3. Seasonal storage energy tank to direct use tank

During periods of high demand and low solar radiation, the solar energy production does not cover the energy demand so the system can use the thermal energy stored in the STES tank through a bypass or using the heat pump to increase the temperature of the buffer tank.

Figure 5: STES tank to buffer tank (Discharging circuit)

However the heat pump can only operate properly under determinate temperature conditions.

In order to make the heat pump operates in an optimal range of temperatures, a bypass circuit has been designed to surround the heat pump if the energy stored in the STES is enough to cover the demand and there is no need to consume electrical energy with the heat pump.

The heat pump only works if WP5 doesn't work (there's no heat transfer directly from the solar thermal collectors) and if both WP3 and WP4 do work under the following conditions:

- If the temperature of the water stored in the STES tank is between 20 °C and 50 °C, the heat pump can increase the temperature of this water to feed the direct use tank.
- When the temperature in the hot side of the STES tank is higher than 20 °C, the WP3 turns ON until the temperature in the hot side is lower than 17 °C. If the temperature in the hot side of the STES tank reaches 50°C, the WP3 turns OFF because the heat pump could not operate properly.
- When the temperature in the cold side of the buffer tank is lower than 55°C, the WP4 turns ON until the temperature reaches the 65°C. If the temperature that comes out of the direct use tank reaches 70°C, the WP4 turns OFF because it's no longer needed to transfer heat to the buffer tank.

Figure 6: STES tank to buffer tank (Discharging circuit using the heat pump)

Otherwise, if the temperature of the water stored in the hot side of the STES is higher than 50 °C, the heat pump could not operate properly. Then, the seasonal tank can feed directly the buffer tank but only in the case that the temperature of the water stored in the hot side of the STES tank is higher than the water in the top side of the direct use tank. Only if these two conditions happen at the same time, and the heat pump is not working, WP7 turns ON.

Figure 7: STES tank to buffer tank (Discharging circuit using the bypass)

Finally, if the temperature of the water stored in the STES tank is lower than 10 °C the heat pump has the risk to have problems due to freezing. To avoid getting to this point, when the temperature on the hot side of the STES tank is lower than 17°C, the WP3 stops so the heat pump does not work.

2.4. Boiler as a backup

Ultimately, if there is heat demand but not enough solar radiation neither energy stored in the STES tank, the boiler can increase the temperature of the water that comes out of the buffer tank in order to achieve the temperature required to cover the demand. When the temperature in the hot side of the direct use tank is lower than 60°C, the boiler turns ON and sets the temperature of the water that will circulate through the system at 60°C. If the temperature that comes out of the buffer tank is higher than 60°C, the boiler turns OFF because it is no longer needed.

Figure 8: Using the boiler to achieve the temperature required

3. System configuration analysis

The object of this section is to determinate the optimal system configuration in terms of energy, cost and comfort. The reference case presented previously has been simulated modifying the parameters of the basic characteristics of its components to adjust the appropriate size of HVAC systems, analyze the energy consumption and calculate the cost of the energy used. The Trnsys energy simulation software has been used for this purpose.

The following parameters have been analysed:

- Modes of operation (Bypass/STES)
- Collector's slope
- Minimum collector's surface to maximize the heat capacity of the seasonal tank
- Storage and buffer tank's thermal losses
- Secondary tank (buffer tank size)
- De/Centralized configuration
- Climate conditions

General considerations:

- The Heat Pump characteristics have been retrieved from the results of the deliverable D3.4.
- A weather file from a town located in the North-East of Spain has been used for the reference case calculations.
- The simulations using the Trnsys software have been done by a period of two years. Only the second year results have been taken into account in this report in order to have reliable data. The time step used is 0.1 hours.
- The energy costs used are the following (source: Eurostat, households 2015. EU-28, 2016s1):
 - Electricity: 0,206 €/kWh
 - Natural Gas: 0,062 €/kWh

3.1. Modes of operation

The aim of this analysis is to know how does the solar energy collected in the STC get to the buffer tank to satisfy the demand comparing the operability and performance of the different modes of operation described in the previous chapter of this report.

The reference case has this schematic representation:

Figure 9: Modes of operation with bypass from STC to buffer

When simulating the reference case in the Trnsys simulation software it is possible to check when does each mode of operation work (represented on the left axis in the Figure 10) and the temperature at which the water comes out the STES (light blue) and the temperature of the water that comes out the buffer tank (dark blue).

Figure 10: Second year system performance with bypass from STC to buffer

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0)³:

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffer tank

As the Figure 10 shows, in January the buffer tank is heated with the heat pump that uses the energy stored in the STES (water >20°C). From February to April and when the temperature of the water stored in the STES tank is under 20°C, the heat pump cannot operate in its best conditions so the boiler turns on to heat the water that comes out of the buffer tank if it goes under 60°C.

In May, when the temperature of the water stored in the STES tank reaches the 20°C again, the heat pump starts operating if there is heat demand. By June, there's no need to use the energy stored in the STES tank because there is solar radiation enough to cover the demand directly (using the bypass), so the water stored increases its temperature until it reaches 90°C. The STES tank discharges energy to the buffer tank through the bypass when the temperature of the stored water is higher than 50°C. Thus, in this case, during October and November the buffer tank is heated by the energy stored in the STES using the bypass. By December, approximately, the temperature in the STES is low enough for the heat pump to work properly so it turns on.

For analysis purposes, it has been also studied the system without the STC to buffer circuit, so all the solar energy collected would be stored in the STES.

³ Control signal is the order sent to the water pumps (WP2 and WP5) and to the Heat Pump to switch them ON or OFF. When the value of the control signal is 1, the elements turn ON and when the control signal is 0, the elements turn OFF.

Figure 11: Modes of operation without bypass from STC to buffer

This system configuration without bypass has also been simulated with the Trnsys simulation software. The results show when does each mode of operation work (left axis in the Figure 12) and the temperature at which the water comes out of the STES (light blue) and the temperature at which the water comes out of the buffer tank (dark blue).

Figure 12: Second year system performance without bypass from STC to buffer

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffer tank

As de Figure 12 shows, the heat pump has to operate from January to June to supply the energy required to cover the demand but, when the temperature of the STES is higher

than 50°C, it stops so the boiler has to turn on until there is enough energy stored in the STES tank to provide energy to the buffer tank.

From July to mid-November, the buffer tank is heated by the energy stored in the STES using the bypass and when the temperature of the STES is lower than 60°C the boiler must turn ON. By mid-December, approximately, the temperature in the STES is low enough for the heat pump to work properly so it turns on.

The results of the simulations of the system carried out with bypass and without it are provided below as well as a comparison of both configurations in terms of energy consumption and energy costs.

Modes of operation comparison

Fixed elements

STC slope = 40°

STC area = 200 m²

STES = 600 m³

Buffer = 30 m³

System configurations

Case 1 (reference case): With bypass from STC to buffer

Case 2: Without bypass from STC to buffer

Modes of operation

These charts show the proportion in which the different modes of operation work for each system configuration analysed (reference case with bypass from STC to buffer and case 2 without bypass from STC to buffer).

Graph 1: Modes of operation for the reference case configuration

For the reference case, the heat pump operates in January, in May and in December. From July to December, there's heat transfer directly from the STES tank to the buffer, without using the heat pump.

Graph 2: Modes of operation for the configuration without bypass from STC to buffer

For the second case without the bypass from STC to Buffer, from January to May the heat pump is operative and from June to November the discharging of the STES tank is made through the bypass. In December the discharging of the STES is made in different proportion by using the heat pump and also the bypass to the buffer tank.

Energy consumption

Graph 3: Energy consumption with and without bypass

Energy savings with bypass compared to no bypass configuration: 15%

Energy costs

Graph 4: Energy costs with and without bypass

Costs savings with bypass compared to no bypass configuration: 46%

Water Pump's energy consumption

Graph 5: Water pumps energy consumption with and without bypass

The energy consumption of the water pumps is higher in the system configuration without the bypass than the energy they consume in the reference case.

3.2. Collector's slope

The solar panel inclination will affect the annual and monthly energy production. In this paragraph it is analysed the energy consumption and energy costs of the reference case varying the slope of the solar panels.

Collector's slope comparison

Fixed elements

STC surface = 200 m²

STES volume = 600 m³

Buffer volume = 30 m³

Variable characteristics

STC slope: 30°, 40°, 45°, 60°, 70° and 90°.

Variable STC slope: 60° from September to March, 45° in April and August and 30° from May to July.

Energy consumption

Graph 6: Energy consumption for different slopes

Variable slope: less energy consumption and major solar energy gain (minimum difference compared to slope at 40°)

Energy savings with variable slope compared to 10° of slope: 35%

Energy savings with variable slope compared to 40° of slope: 5%

Energy savings with variable slope compared to 60° of slope: 10%

Energy savings with variable slope compared to 90° of slope: 61%

Energy costs

Graph 7: Energy costs for different slopes

Slope 40° less energy cost

Energy savings with 40° of slope compared to 10° of slope: 16%

Energy savings with 40° of slope compared to variable slope: 1%

Energy savings with 40° of slope compared to 60° of slope: 13%

Energy savings with 40° of slope compared to 90° of slope: 37%

3.3. Minimum collector's surface to maximize the heat capacity of the seasonal tank

The purpose of this section is to determine the minimum collector's surface and the optimal size of the storage tank.

A total of nine different system configurations have been analysed in detail using the Trnsys simulation software and are listed below. The graphical results are provided in Annex 1: Trnsys simulation graphs results of this report.

Each simulation code indicates the Solar Thermal Collectors surface (STC), Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage (STES) tank volume and Buffer tank volume. For example System configuration 15030030 means:

Solar thermal collector surface=150m²

Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage tank volume=300m³

Buffer tank volume=30m³

Minimum Collectors surface and maximum STES tank heat capacity

- **15030030**: STC=150m², STES=300m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 13.
- **15060030**: STC=150m², STES=600m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 14.
- **20030030**: STC=200m², STES=300m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 15.
- **20045030**: STC=200m², STES=450m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 16.
- **20060030**: STC=200m², STES=600m³ and Buffer=30m³(reference case). See Figure 17.
- **20080030**: STC=200m², STES=800m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 18.
- **30030030**: STC=300m², STES=300m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 19.
- **40030030**: STC=400m², STES=300m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 20.
- **40060030**: STC=400m², STES=600m³ and Buffer=30m³. See Figure 21.

The energy consumption, the energy cost, the investment and the payback period of the different system configurations are studied below.

It should be taken into account that this analysis has been conducted considering a certain demand profile in a concrete location. The results would be different if the weather conditions and the energy demand varies from these assumptions.

STC and STES dimensions comparison

Fixed elements

STC slope = 40°

Buffer volume= 30 m³

Variable characteristics

STC surface= 150m², 200m², 300m² and 400m²

STES volume = 300 m³, 450 m³, 600 m³ and 800 m³

Energy consumption

Graph 8: Energy consumption for different STC and STES dimensions

Optimal configuration⁴: STC=400m², STES=300m³ Buffer=30m³ 59% Total

Energy savings of 40030030 compared to reference case 20060030 84% (boiler)

Energy costs

Graph 9: Energy costs for different STC and STES dimensions

⁴ Although the results show that the best system configuration in terms of energy is 40060030, the heat pump, which is one of the main elements of the CHES-SETUP Project, does not operate. This configuration behaves as a conventional solar system and does not comply with the objectives of the project. Thus, it is not considered as the optimal solution.

Optimal configuration: $STC=400m^2$, $STES=300m^3$ Buffer= $30m^3$

Costs savings of 40030030 compared to reference case 20060030: 36% Total

Investment

Graph 10: Investment for different STC and STES dimensions

Although the configuration 15030030 implies the lowest investment, it has been seen that it is the option with the highest energy consumption. The optimal configuration investment is 36% lower than the investment of the reference case (considering only the investment in STC and STES for each configuration).

Payback

Graph 11: Payback period for different STC and STES dimensions

It can be seen that the configuration 40030030 has the lowest payback period (14,3 years).

3.4. Storage and buffer tank's thermal losses

The shape and the materials of the storage system can affect to thermal losses, heat transmission properties, stratification and investment costs.

The aim of this analysis it to quantify the energy losses considering completely insulated tanks and tanks with a certain coefficient of losses, taking into account its location, if they are in contact with the air at ambient temperature, in contact with the soil or inside an enclosed space.

Thermal losses comparison

Fixed elements

STC slope = 40°

STC = 200 m²

STES = 600 m³

Buffer = 30 m³

Variable characteristics

Ambient temperature: fixed at 10°C , fixed at 15°C and hourly measured data.

Losses coefficient STES tank and buffer tank: 0 W/m²K (ideal) and 0.1 W/m²K (70cm).

Thermal losses

Graph 12: Tank's thermal losses under different ambient temperatures

Given the climate condition of the reference case, thermal losses are lower if the STES and buffer tanks are placed underground or in an enclosed space at a constant temperature of 15°C. In this analysis the tank located at 15°C has a 7% less of thermal losses than a tank in constant to ambient temperature.

3.5. Direct use tank size (buffer tank)

The purpose of this analysis is to quantify the energy saving varying the size of the buffer tank.

The size of the buffer tank will affect the performance of the heat pump and the natural gas boiler because its dimension influences in its capacity to storage the energy that is going to be delivered to the system.

Buffer tank size comparison

Fixed elements

STC slope = 40°

Variable characteristics

STC = 200 m² and 400 m²

STES = 300 m³ and 600 m³

Buffer = 30 m³ and 12 m³

Energy consumption

Graph 13: Energy consumption for different buffer tank sizes

STC=200m², STES=600m³ and Buffer=30m³

Energy savings compared to 12m³ of buffer capacity: 6%

STC=400m², STES=300m³ and Buffer=30m³

Energy savings compared to 12m³ of buffer capacity: 25%

Energy costs

Graph 14: Energy costs for different buffer tank sizes

Reference case $STC=200m^2$, $STES=600m^3$ Buffer= $30m^3$

Costs savings compared to $12m^3$ of buffer capacity: 29%

$STC=400m^2$, $STES=300m^3$ and Buffer= $12m^3$

Costs savings compared to $30m^3$ of buffer capacity: 16%

3.6. De/Centralized configuration

The aim of this section is to make a simplified comparison between a centralized system and a decentralized one, on the understanding that a centralized system refers to a configuration where the final emitters are close to the CHES-SETUP system facilities.

Centralized and decentralized configurations comparison

Fixed elements

STC slope = 40°

Variable characteristics

STC = $200 m^2$ and $400 m^2$

$STES$ = $300 m^3$ and $600 m^3$

Distance from buffer tank to boiler service facilities:
 10 meters and 200 meters

Centralized configuration

Decentralized configuration

Energy consumption

Graph 15: Energy consumption for centralized and decentralized configurations

Reference case configuration: STC=200m², STES=600m³ Buffer=30m³

Energy savings centralized system compared to decentralized system: 2,2%

Optimal configuration: STC=400m², STES=300m³ Buffer=30m³

Energy savings centralized system compared to decentralized system: 1,9%

Energy costs

Graph 16: Energy costs for centralized and decentralized configurations

Reference case configuration: STC=200m², STES=600m³ Buffer=30m³

Costs savings centralized system compared to decentralized system: 1,9%

Optimal configuration: STC=400m², STES=300m³ Buffer=30m³

Costs savings centralized system compared to decentralized system: 2,5%

3.7. Climate conditions

As mentioned in the previous sections, climate conditions may affect the system behaviour. In this sense, two different system configurations have been analysed using the Trnsys simulation software for three different climate conditions that are listed below. For the North-east of Spain the data proceed from the Catalan Weather Service, while the Stockholm and London weather information was taken from TM2 file in Trnsys system files. The graphical results are provided in Annex 1: Trnsys simulation graphs results of this report.

System configurations:

- **20060030**: STC=200m², STES=600m³ and Buffer=30m³.

Climate conditions:

- **North-East of Spain**: latitude 42° (reference case). See Figure 22.

- **Stockholm**: latitude 59,3° . See Figure 23.

- **London:** latitude 51,5°. See Figure 24.
- **40030030:** STC=400m², STES=300m³ and Buffer=30m³.

Climate conditions:

- **North-East of Spain:** latitude 42° (reference case). See Figure 25.
- **Stockholm:** latitude 59,3° . See Figure 26.
- **London:** latitude 51,5°. See Figure 27.

The following Graph 17 and Graph 18 show the energy consumption and costs of these two configurations with the three different weather conditions analysed.

Graph 17: Energy consumption under different climate conditions

The energy consumption of the system 20060030 in the reference case location (north-East of Spain) increases a 45% if the same system is implanted in Stockholm and a 51% if the location it is located in London. The reference case has a 75% energy saving when compared to the system implanted in Stockholm and London.

These results stated that the weather conditions are closely related to the energy consumption of the system. Thus, the system parameters will have to be readjusted if the location where it is implanted has different climate conditions.

Graph 18: Energy costs under different climate conditions

For the system configuration 20060030, the costs savings in the reference case in relation with Stockholm are around 28% and the energy savings in the reference case in relation with the system implanted in London are approximately 34%. The reference case has a 49% cost saving when compared to the system implanted in Stockholm and London.

4. System configuration conclusions

The optimal configuration is a system with the following modes of operation and parameters for the climate conditions and demands analysed in the reference case.

Table 3: Basic characteristics of the elements on the optimal case configuration

Elements and data	Basic characteristics on the optimal case configuration
Location	North-East of Spain (latitude 42°) Enclosed space: 15°C Total annual irradiation on horizontal: 1.693 kWh/m ² Operation hours/year: 8760 hr Peak load: 173,2 kW
Total demand	Heat and hot water demand: 263.655,9 kW/year (100 family units)
Solar Thermal Collector (STC)	Collectors surface: 400m ² Orientation: south Slope: 40°

Elements and data	Basic characteristics on the optimal case configuration
Heat transfer fluid (solar collectors)	Water
Heat Exchanger	Plate heat exchanger Performance: 100%
Seasonal Storage Tank (STES)	Volume = 300m ³ Cylindrical shape
Heat Pump	Thermal capacity: 905.750 kJ/hr Power capacity: 270.857 kJ/hr Water flow: 4.8l/s (evaporator) and 8.3l/s (condenser)
Direct Use Tank (Buffer tank)	Volume: 0.1 x Volume Storage tank = 30 m ³ Cylindrical shape
Boiler	Maximum heating rate: 400.000 kJ/hr

4.1. Modes of operation

The STES bypass allows charging the buffer tank directly from STC providing energy savings around 15% and cost saving around 40% for the reference case.

The optimal system configuration (with bypass from STC to buffer) has 56% energy saving compared to the system without the bypass. Related to the energy cost, there is not much difference between the two configurations.

It is also noted that the water pumps in the system with bypass consume less energy than in the system without bypass.

Graph 19: Energy consumption with and without bypass for the optimal configuration

Graph 20: Energy costs with and without bypass for the optimal configuration

4.2. Collectors' slope

The solar energy gains are the highest by installing solar panels with variable slope. The system consumes less energy also with solar panels with variable slope. However both values are closer to the results obtained with the panels at 40°.

In this sense, and considering that the variable slope will increase the budget in terms of the installation and the maintenance operations, the inclination of the collectors is 40° in the optimal configuration.

4.3. Collectors' surface

The STES keeps the water stored at a higher temperature for a long period of time when duplicating the STC surface and service temperature (buffer outlet temperature) is more stable with larger panels' area (see Figure 20 in section 5).

The optimal configuration, with larger STC surface, has 59% energy savings compared to the reference case.

The optimal configuration has the lowest payback period (14,3 years) while the reference case payback period is 27,6 years.

4.4. Thermal losses

For the reference case, a STES tank placed underground or in an enclosed space (15°C) has 7% less thermal losses than if it is exposed to ambient temperature (losses coefficient considered: 0.1 W/m²k).

When decreasing the STES tank size in the optimal configuration the thermal losses increase 23% referring to the STES and 8% referring to the buffer tank compared to the reference case.

Graph 21: Thermal losses for the reference and optimal configuration

However, as it has been seen in the previous sections, the total energy savings are higher and the energy costs are lower for the optimal configuration.

4.5. Direct use tank

While the energy costs are similar between using a buffer tank of 30m³ and 12m³ in the 400300 configuration, the 30m³ buffer tank's option has higher energy savings respect the 12m³.

4.6. De/centralized system

For the optimal configuration, increasing the distance from the centralized system to the service facility (from 10 meters to 200 meters), implies that energy consumption increases 1,9% and energy costs increase 2,5%.

4.7. Climate conditions

As stated in the previous sections, the results are closely related to the place where the system is located and the energy demand of the building. Thus, the parameters analysed may have to be readjusted for each demand profile and the weather conditions.

According to the results obtained from analysing two different configurations in three different locations, a colder weather affects on the behaviour of the system increasing the energy consumption and the energy costs of it.

5. Annex 1: Trnsys simulation graphs results

Minimum Collectors surface and maximum STES tank heat capacity

System configuration 15030030: STC=150 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 13: System configuration 15030030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 15060030: STC=150 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 14: System configuration 15060030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 20030030: STC=200 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 15: System configuration 20030030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

- STES to Buffer
- STES to HP
- Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

- STES tank
- Buffertank

System configuration 20045030: STC=200 m², STES=450 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 16: System configuration 20045030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

- STES to Buffer
- STES to HP
- Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

- STES tank
- Buffertank

System configuration 20060030: STC=200 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 17: System configuration 20060030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 20080030: STC=200 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 18: System configuration 20080030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 30030030: STC=300 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 19: System configuration 30030030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 40030030: STC=400 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 20: System configuration 40030030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 40060030: STC=400 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 21: System configuration 40060030 performance

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

Climate conditions

System configuration 20060030 latitude 42° (reference case): STC=200 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 22: System configuration 20060030 performance reference case

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 20060030 latitude 59,4° (Stockholm): STC=200 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 23: System configuration 20060030 performance in Stockholm

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 20060030 latitude 51,5° (London): STC=200 m², STES=600 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 24: System configuration 20060030 performance in London

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 40030030 latitude 42° (reference case): STC=400 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 25: System configuration 40030030 performance reference case

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 40030030 latitude 59,4° (Stockholm): STC=400 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 26: System configuration 40030030 performance in Stockholm

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

System configuration 40030030 latitude 51,5° (London): STC=400 m², STES=300 m³ and Buffer=30 m³

Figure 27: System configuration 40030030 performance in London

Control signal (ON=1 or OFF=0):

■ STES to Buffer ■ STES to HP ■ Boiler

Outlet Temperatures:

■ STES tank ■ Buffertank

6. Annex 2: Trnsys types

Type 16: This instance of Type16 takes hourly integrated values of total horizontal solar radiation and computes the diffuse fraction using an algorithm that estimates cloudiness based on dry bulb and dew point temperature.

Table 4: Solar radiation processor parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Horiz. radiation mode	2	-
Tracking mode	1	-
Tilted surface mode	4	-
Starting day	1	day
Latitude	42.0025817	-
Solar constant	4871	kJ/hr.m ²
Shift in solar time	0	degrees
Not used	2	-
Solar time?	-1	-

Type 15-6: This component serves the purpose of reading data at regular time intervals from an external weather data file, interpolating the data (including solar radiation for tilted surfaces) at timesteps of less than one hour, and making it available to other TRNSYS components. The model also calculates several useful terms including the mains water temperature, the effective sky temperature, and the heating and cooling season forcing functions.

This component reads weather data files in the following formats: Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) format (.TMY), Typical Meteorological Year Version 2 (TMY2) format (.TM2), Typical Meteorological Year Version 3 (TMY3) format (.TMY3), International Weather for Energy Calculations (IWECC) format, Canadian Weather for Energy Calculations (CWECC) format, Energy+ format (.EPW), Meteornorm files for TRNSYS (.TM2), German 2004 and 2010 TRY formats.

Table 5: Weather data processor parameters

Name	Value	Unit
File Type	6	-
Logical unit	58	-
Tilted Surface Radiation Mode	3	-
Ground reflectance - no snow	0.2	-
Ground reflectance - snow cover	0.7	-
Number of surfaces	1	-
Tracking mode	1	-
Slope of surface	40	degrees
Azimuth of surface	0	degrees

Type 9e: This component serves the purpose of reading data at regular time intervals from a data file, converting it to a desired system of units, and making it available to other TRNSYS components as time-varying forcing functions.

Table 6: Demand file parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Mode	2	-
Header Lines to Skip	1	-
No. of values to read	2	-
Time interval of data	1.0	hr
Interpolate or not-1	1	-
Multiplication factor-1	1.0	-
Addition factor-1	0	-
Average or instantaneous value-1	1	-
Interpolate or not-2	1	-
Multiplication factor-2	1.0	-
Addition factor-2	0	-
Average or instantaneous value-2	1	-

Name	Value	Unit
Logical unit for input file	51	-
Free format mode	-1	-

Graph 22: Annual energy demand of the reference case

The above figure shows the summary of the annual energy demand of the 100-family units reference case used.

Type 539: This component sets the flow rate for all connected flow loop components if the variable speed option is enabled.

Table 7: Solar Thermal Collectors parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Number in series	1	-
Collector area	Area_Captacion	string
Fluid specific heat	4.19	kJ/kg.K
Collector test mode	1	-
Intercept efficiency (a ₀)	0.81	-
1st order efficiency coefficient (a ₁)	1.61	kJ/hr.m ² .K
2nd order efficiency coefficient (a ₂)	0.008	kJ/hr.m ² .K ²
Tested flow rate per unit area	Cabal_test_capt	string
Fluid specific heat at test conditions	4.19	kJ/kg.K

Name	Value	Unit
1st-order IAM coefficient	0.1	-
2nd-order IAM coefficient	0.0	-
Minimum flowrate	0.0	kg/hr
Maximum flowrate	10000.0	kg/hr
Capacitance of Collector	60	kJ/K
Number of Nodes	5	-
Initial Temperature	10	C

Type 91b: A zero capacitance sensible heat exchanger is modeled as a constant effectiveness device which is independent of the system configuration.

Table 8: Heat Exchanger parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Specific heat of source side fluid	4.19	kJ/kg.K
Specific heat of load side fluid	4.19	kJ/kg.K

Type 4a: The thermal performance of a fluid-filled sensible energy storage tank, subject to thermal stratification, can be modeled by assuming that the tank consists of N (N <= 100) fully-mixed equal volume segments. The degree of stratification is determined by the value of N. If N is equal to 1, the storage tank is modeled as a fully-mixed tank and no stratification effects are possible. This instance of Type 4 models a stratified tank having fixed inlet positions defined within the code.

Table 9: STES tank parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Fixed inlet positions	1	-
Tank volume	VOL_STE	string
Fluid specific heat	4.190	kJ/kg.K
Fluid density	1000.0	kg/m ³
Tank loss coefficient	0	kJ/hr.m ² .K
Height of node-1	Altura_STE	string

Name	Value	Unit
Height of node-2	Altura_N2	string
Height of node-3	Altura_N3	string
Height of node-4	Altura_N4	string
Height of node-5	0.5	m
Auxiliary heater mode	1	-
Node containing heating element 1	1	degrees
Node containing thermostat 1	1	-
Set point temperature for element 1	20	C
Deadband for heating element 1	5.0	deltaC
Maximum heating rate of element 1	0	kJ/hr
Node containing heating element 2	1	-
Node containing thermostat 2	1	-
Set point temperature for element 2	20	C
Deadband for heating element 2	5.0	deltaC
Maximum heating rate of element 2	0	kJ/hr
Not used (Flue UA)	0.0	W/K
Not used (Tflue)	20.0	C
Boiling point	100.0	C

Type 927: This component models a single-stage water-to-water heat pump. The heat pump conditions a liquid stream by rejecting energy to (cooling mode) or absorbing energy from (heating mode) a second liquid stream. This model is based on user-supplied data files containing catalog data for the normalized capacity and power draw, based on the entering load and source temperatures and the normalized source and load flowrates. Type927 operates in temperature level control much like an actual heat pump would; when the user defined control signal indicates that the unit should be on in either heating or cooling mode, it operates at its capacity level until the control signal values changes.

Table 10: Heat pump parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Source fluid specific heat	4.190	kJ/kg.K
Load fluid specific heat	4.190	kJ/kg.K
Source fluid density	1000.	kg/m ³
Load fluid density	1000.	kg/m ³
Logical unit number for cooling data file	49	-
Number of source temperatures - cooling	8	-
Number of load temperatures - cooling	4	-
Logical unit for heating data	50	-
Number of source temps. - heating	5	-
Number of load temps. - heating	4	-
Number of source flow rates	3	-
Number of load flow rates	3	-
Rated cooling capacity per heat pump	30000	kJ/hr
Rated cooling power per heat pump	6000	kJ/hr
Rated heating capacity per heat pump	905750	kJ/hr
Rated heating power per heat pump	270857	kJ/hr
Rated source flow rate per heat pump	4.8	l/s
Rated load flow rate per heat pump	8.3	l/s
Number of identical heat pumps	1	-

Type 4a: The thermal performance of a fluid-filled sensible energy storage tank, subject to thermal stratification, can be modeled by assuming that the tank consists of N ($N \leq 100$) fully-mixed equal volume segments. The degree of stratification is determined by the value of N . If N is equal to 1, the storage tank is modeled as a fully-mixed tank and no stratification effects are possible. This instance of Type 4 models a stratified tank having fixed inlet positions defined within the code.

Table 11: Buffer tank parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Fixed inlet positions	1	-
Tank volume	Vol_buffer	string
Fluid specific heat	4.190	kJ/kg.K
Fluid density	1000.0	kg/m ³
Tank loss coefficient	0	kJ/hr.m ² .K
Height of node-1	0.5	m
Height of node-2	1	m
Height of node-3	0.5	m
Auxiliary heater mode	1	-
Node containing heating element 1	1	-
Node containing thermostat 1	1	-
Set point temperature for element 1	55.0	C
Deadband for heating element 1	5.0	deltaC
Maximum heating rate of element 1	0	kJ/hr
Node containing heating element 2	1	-
Node containing thermostat 2	1	-
Set point temperature for element 2	55.0	C
Deadband for heating element 2	5.0	deltaC
Maximum heating rate of element 2	0	kJ/hr
Not used (Flue UA)	0.0	W/K
Not used (Tflue)	20.0	C
Boiling point	100.0	C
Tank volume	Vol_buffer	string
Fluid specific heat	4.190	kJ/kg.K

Type 6: An auxiliary heater is modeled to elevate the temperature of a flow stream using either internal control, external control or a combination of both types of control. The heater is designed to add heat to the flow stream at a user-designated rate (Q_{max}) whenever the external control input is equal to one and the heater outlet temperature is less than a user-specified maximum (T_{set}). By specifying a constant value of the control function of one and specifying a sufficiently large value of Q_{max} , this routine will perform like a domestic hot water auxiliary with internal control to maintain an outlet temperature of T_{set} .

Table 12: Auxiliary Heater parameters

Name	Value	Unit
Maximum heating rate	400000	kJ/hr
Specific heat of fluid	4.19	kJ/kg.K
Overall loss coefficient for heater during operation	0.0	kJ/hr.K
Efficiency of auxiliary heater	1.0	-

